

DEVELOPMENT STAGE OF BOXING AND ITS TECHNIQUE.

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Abstract: The history of the emergence and development of boxing . Emergence of boxing as a sport. Boxing in the USA, England, Egypt, Ancient Greece . The formation and development of boxing in Russia before the revolution . Development of boxing in Uzbekistan. The role of boxers in World War II. Achievements of boxers of Uzbekistan in the Olympic Games, world and European championships. Boxing techniques. Summation of attack and defense methods, general understanding of boxing technique. Definition, classification and terminology of boxing techniques. Boxer movement technique system, criteria and (quantity of quality) effectiveness.

Key words: Boxer movement technique system, strength, speed, endurance, agility, flexibility, stability.

Introduction: Stability, variability (severe change) of the technique and characteristic of its styles, attack and defense techniques. Techniques of deception, counterattack, defense and strikes at close, medium and long distances. A set of movement techniques, mission battles. Fighting with chapakai boxers and the uniqueness of the technique of chapakai boxers. Task-free battles. Free battles. Sparring. Boxing tactics. General understanding of boxing tactics. The art of fighting techniques in the ring. The importance of tactics in achieving victory. Battle planning. A component of tactics: battle development. To test the opponent in battle is to conduct reconnaissance, to determine and organize a solution to conduct a battle , to prevent unexpected situations. Commentary on tactical tasks in the ring. Tactical situations in battle. A boxer's ability to think tactically: the ability of an athlete to

quickly receive and process information in a fight, to find the best tactical solutions that differ from each other. Methodology of teaching boxing skills. General principles of the methodology of teaching movement skills. Purpose and tasks of teaching. Characteristics of the application of didactic principles in the process of training in boxing : principles of scientificity, awareness and activity, instructiveness, affordability, regularity and excellence. The order and stages of the training process : initial, "in-depth", perfecting, improvement stages. The purpose and tasks of the initial stage in teaching the techniques of combat skills . Teaching methods and tools. Fighting and competition styles. Monitoring and evaluation of teaching effectiveness. Physical qualities of boxers.

Relevance of the topic: The basic concept of hard work in boxing . Boxer's Physical Qualities: Strength, Speed, Endurance, Agility, Flexibility, Vestibular Dominance and Explanation of Physical Qualities. Strength. An indicator of character tensions in boxing, depending on the characteristics of fighting in a combat situation . Speed. Its main forms of appearance in boxing . The speed of individual blows, the requirements for the intensity of their impact, the speed of simple and complex exposure. The relationship between accuracy and speed. Endurance. Identifying it. General and special endurance, their dependence. The passage of endurance. Physiological mechanism of endurance. Endurance criterion. An overview of agility skills. When fighting one-on-one (individual) in the ring: the formation of emerging agility skills. Flexibility. Factors forming flexibility and its explanation. The appearance of flexibility in a boxer . A general understanding of vestibular dominance. Formation in the career of a boxer. Education of physical qualities. Means and methods of education of physical qualities . Peculiarities of training and organization of physical qualities in boxing . Rules of the competition and its conduct. The essence of the competition: the competition as the main form in the organization of sports; Conclusion to sports activities: Encouragement to increase sports skills, promotional and educational activities of the competition. The rules of the competition, its origin and influence on the technique and tactics of

boxers. Open competitions, championships, qualifiers. Nature and types of competition. Contestants. Competition fight, work of judges. Carrying out boxing competitions, weighing. Divide into pairs . Ways to determine the winner and circumstances of awarding the prize. Competition regulations. Mental qualities of a boxer The essence of mental qualities in the skills of boxers. Conditional level of the characteristics of the development of mental qualities of a boxer in sports and specific movement activities. Boxer's development, thinking ability, noteworthy features. Characteristics of normal sensorimotor (influence of the sense organ on movement) , dysenctive (complex), anticipatory (precognitive) sensitivity. The main causes (motive) of emotional characteristics are specific.

Discussion part of the topic: Specificity of information to the system of psychic tension. Competition. A sample explanation of the mental state during training. An understanding of the mental conditioning and conditioning of a boxer. Dynamics of mental preparation. Methodology of conducting competitions in boxing circles. Selection is a long-term (multi -year) process. Arrangements for the organization of the primary competition for admission to sports schools and the conditions and methods of conducting it. Prospective (perspective) competition, its tasks, conducting procedure, conditions. Taking into account genetic abilities in the competition, predicting the future talent and skills of children based on the results of the competition. Taking into account the "combat specialization" model of boxers during the selection and preliminary training stage. Practical training. Practical training is focused on combat techniques and tactics, tactical actions in attack and defense, development of physical qualities, formation of professional and pedagogical qualifications and skills, and perfect mastery of theoretical knowledge. General understanding of boxing technique. Attack technique. Defense technique. Counter attack technique. Defenses: defense techniques using arms, body and legs. Tactics for close, medium and long range combat. The tactics of fighting against the Chapakay boxer. Fighting tactics against a fast boxer. Methodology of taking tests for the boxing sport. Development of general and special physical qualities.

Formation of fighting skills and skills during boxing training. Formation of skills in organizing and conducting boxing competitions. Formation of skills of refereeing competitions as a referee of various kinds . Formation of team leadership skills in competitions . The dimensions of the ring. Length 4.90 cm to 6.10 cm, ring rope thickness 2.5 cm, height 132.1 cm (from the floor to the rope 40.6 cm, the distance between the second, third and fourth ropes is 30, 5 cm to a total of 132.1 cm), the height of the ring from the ground is 1 m. The first officially recorded champion is the famous English boxer James Figg (1719–1743). The first book about boxing was written by his student John Broughton. Boxing as a sport has been included in the program of the Olympic Games since 1904. The World Boxing Championship is held every 4 years. Competitions are held depending on the age of children, for example: 17 weight categories are designated for 12-14-year-old boxers : 36, 38, 40, 42, 44, 46, 48, 50, 52, 54, 57, 60, 63, 6, 70, 75, 80. 15 weight categories for boxers aged 15-16 years : 42, 44, 46, 48, 50, 52, 54, 57, 63, 66, 70, 74, 80, 86. 17-18 years old 13 weight categories are designated for boxers : 44, 46, 48, 51, 54, 57, 60, 64, 69, 75, 81, 91, +91. There are 10 weight categories for men's elite and juniors : 49, 52, 56, 60, 64, 69, 75, 81, 91, +91. For women's elite and young women, 3 weight categories are designated : 48-54 kg, 60-64 kg, 70-75 kg. After the punch, the boxer needs to maintain a strong position in order not to lose his fighting ability and not to be open to the counterattack blows of the opponent. In all cases, the body should not be thrown out of the front border of the support when hitting. After the punch, the boxer must return to the fighting position, for this it is necessary to: 1) bring the back leg to the fighting standing position. In this case, UOM falls in the middle of the base area ; 2) push off from the front leg and push the body back. In this case, the UOM projection moves to the middle of the base area. Proper footwork helps the boxer maintain balance, which means he can move from one move to another quickly and efficiently.

Conclusion: Boxer must be careful of the opponent's possible counterattacks when performing a blow . For this, he needs to cover his chin and body with his free

hand. Boxing rules only allow punches with a clenched fist in a soft, padded boxing glove (8–10 oz). During the impact, the paw takes a lot of load, so it should be clenched with a proper fist. The main reason for injuries to the paw and its ligaments is the wrong position of the fist during the impact. The position of the punched paw should be as follows : the fingers are bent and pressed into the palm, the thumb is pressed into the middle phalanx of the index finger. The heads of the wrist bones serve as the striking surface of the fist . They face vertical pressure during impact. In the initial position of the stroke, the fingers are not strained.

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